

LUMBAR VERTEBRAL FRACTURE MIMMICKING DISC PROLAPSE

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Abstract

Introduction: A lumbar vertebrae fracture is most often caused by severe trauma, like a car accident or fall, but also by osteoporosis, leading to pain, instability, and potentially nerve damage like weakness or numbness. Treatment typically involves conservative methods like bracing and physical therapy, though in some cases, surgical interventions such as vertebroplasty may be necessary to stabilize the spine. A lumbar-sacral disc prolapses or herniated disc is a condition where nucleus pulposus of an intervertebral disc in the lower back pushes through annulus fibrosus. This displaced disc material can press on nearby nerve roots, leading to symptoms like sciatica, back pain, leg pain, numbness, and weakness. While often caused by aging and wear and tear, it can also result from a severe injury. Most cases resolve with conservative treatment, but emergency surgery is needed for severe symptoms like bowel or bladder incontinence

Case report: A seventy-five-year-old female was on regular treatment for hypertension and hypothyroidism for last 30 years. She was treated over a period of last five years for gastro-esophageal reflux disease with proton pump inhibitors and prokinetic combination and had lower serum calcium levels for prolonged period for which she was being treated regularly with oral calcium. She had twice recovered from covid -19 infection & sciatica pain and was later on diagnosed to be having heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HfPEF). One day while weighing herself on weighing machine, she slipped and developed mild backache for which analgesic with anti-inflammatory but for no relief. She for getting relief started getting massaged on back by homemade massager by domestic help which aggravated the problem. At this stage she was subjected to MRI lumbosacral spine which revealed compression fracture at L2 level with disc at L4-L5 level but there was no local tenderness at L2 level which forced to attribute problem to prolapsed intervertebral disc at L4-L5 level. She was advised complete bed rest and hence was put on sanitary diaper but she was not able to perceive over wetting of diaper, thus was catheterized. She also developed obstipation for five days. She was not able to sit due to excruciating pain. One day, she was made to walk with waist belt and supporting from both the sides but she was not able to walk even few steps. After a gap of two days, she was made to sit on bed with support but developed excruciating pain, complete loss of power in bilateral lower limbs along with hyperemia. She was immediately made to lie down and had partial motor recovery in left lower limb only. In view of development of suspected cord compression, she was given one-gram injectable methyl prednisolone and admitted under Neurosurgery care. The repeat MRI at this point of time showed previous finding with addition of cord edema. She underwent emergency operation in which spinal cord was decompressed by removal of vertebral fracture pieces and stabilization of L2 vertebra by cement application and fixation of screws in T12, L1, L3 and L4. Post-operatively, it was clear that she had bladder and bowel involvement also. She was started on regular physiotherapy and Kigel's exercises for improvement of bladder and bowel involvement. Pre-operatively, she was on oral diuretics for control of hypertension and heart failure but post-operatively due to injectable steroids for reducing cord edema, she was having excessive diuresis, thus oral diuretics were stopped. On third post-operative day, she developed cough with mild breathlessness, thus urgent chest x-ray was done which revealed pulmonary edema which got relieved within two days of restart of oral diuretics. After discharge from hospital on fifth post-operative day, she was started on oral anticoagulants for prevention of deep venous thrombosis which led to fall in hemoglobin. Her baseline total proteins were also low which further dropped post-operatively. Both anemia and hypoproteinemia limited the post-operative physiotherapy. Thus, for early increase in hemoglobin and serum protein level, she was transfused two whole blood and six intravenous albumins, over period of five days. But in view of her baseline heart failure and transfusions over rapid speed in short period, she went into left heart failure. She was treated with high dose of injectable diuretics, bisoprolol, valsartan & sacubitril and oxygen therapy. She gradually improved over a period of ten days. After six months post-operatively, the power is improved in bilateral lower limbs and she can walk with help of walker and there is partial recovery in bladder and bowel.

Conclusion: The symptoms of vertebral fractures sometimes can lead to confusion with intervertebral disc prolapse and have to be differentiated on priority basis for preventing damage to spinal cord, leading to permanent neurological deficit.

Keywords: Vertebral fracture, Disc prolapse, Cord edema, Laminectomy, Cement, MRI

INTRODUCTION- A lumbar fracture can mimic a disc prolapse, especially after trauma, with case reports describing a vertebral fracture being identified only after initial imaging like CT or MRI revealed an epidural mass or disc herniation. This occurs because a fracture can cause a disc to herniate, and the resulting disc fragments may appear similar to other spinal pathologies like tumours or epidural hematomas on imaging, requiring careful evaluation to determine the underlying cause. Trauma, such as a fall or crushing injury, can cause both a vertebral fracture and a disc herniation simultaneously. On a CT scan, the fracture might be the initial finding, but an MRI may subsequently show an epidural mass that could be mistaken for a disc herniation or other spinal issue. The herniated disc material, sometimes described as a "mass" on imaging, can mimic other spinal conditions like tumours or epidural hematomas, confusing the diagnosis. A patient's symptoms, like leg pain, may not always correlate perfectly with either a simple disc prolapse or a fracture alone. Diagnosing a large lumbar disc herniation can be challenging, as a severe disc herniation often mimics spinal tumours, traumatic lesions or from other causes of lumbar canal stenosis, such as synovial cysts, epidural hematomas and metastases [1]. Sequestered disc herniations generally appear as heterogeneously hypo- to isointense on T1- and T2-weighted MRI images [2]. MRI with gadolinium injection is useful for differentiating a disc herniation from tumours and other epidural lesions, as the disc fragment typically shows peripheral enhancement. A herniated disc fragment rarely presents central enhancement, due to vascular granulation tissue infiltrating the fragment, but it is never associated with enhancement of the spinal meninges, a characteristic of neoplastic lesions such as lymphoma and neurofibroma [2].

CASE REPORT- A seventy-five-year-old female was on regular treatment for hypertension and hypothyroidism for last 30 years. She was treated over a period of last five years for gastro-esophageal reflux disease with proton pump inhibitors and pro-kinetic combination and had lower serum calcium levels for prolonged period for which she was being treated regularly with oral calcium. She had twice recovered from covid -19 infection & sciatica pain and was later on diagnosed to be having heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HfPEF). One day while weighing herself on weighing machine, she slipped and developed mild backache for which analgesic with anti-inflammatory but for no relief. She for getting relief started getting massaged on back by homemade massager by domestic help which aggravated the problem. At this stage she was subjected to MRI lumbosacral spine which revealed degenerative changes in lumbar spine with partial collapse of L2 vertebra likely osteoporotic without significant marrow edema. The posterior bulging cortex of the L2 vertebra was causing effacement of the anterior sub-arachnoid space and indentation of the cauda equina nerve roots and conus. Small disc bulges were seen in L4-5 and L5-S1 levels with bilateral ligamentum flavum thickening and facet arthropathy causing thecal sac indentation and bilateral lateral recess neural foramina narrowing. Resultant abutment of bilateral L5 existing nerve roots was seen. She was advised complete bed rest and hence was put on sanitary diaper but she was not able to perceive over wetting of diaper, thus was catheterized. She also developed obstipation for five days. She was not able to sit due to excruciating pain. One day, she was made to walk with waist belt and supporting from both the sides but she was not able to walk even few steps. After a gap of two days, she was made to sit on bed with support but developed excruciating pain, complete loss of power in bilateral lower limbs along with hyperemia. She was immediately made to lie down and had partial motor recovery in left lower limb only. In view of development of suspected cord compression, she was given one-gram injectable methyl prednisolone and admitted under Neurosurgery care. The repeat MRI at this point of time showed previous finding with addition of cord edema. She underwent emergency operation in which spinal cord was decompressed by removal of vertebral fracture pieces and stabilization of L2 vertebra by cement

application and fixation of screws in T12 L1, L3 and L4. Post-operatively, it was clear that she had bladder and bowel involvement also. She was started on regular physiotherapy and Kigel's exercises for improvement of bladder and bowel involvement. The third MRI done post-operatively after one month revealed trans pedicular screws at D12-L4 level with adjacent susceptibility artifacts. T2/T1 hypointense bone cement in L2 vertebral body with T2/STIR hyperintense suspicious collection seen in posterior part of L2 vertebral body with extension into left pedicle, measuring 23mm X 11 mm X 12 mm with adjacent marrow edema. STIR hyperintense and T1 hypointense signal intensity in D12 vertebral body? Infective? inflammatory. After six months post-operatively, the power is improved in bilateral lower limbs and she can walk with help of walker and there is partial recovery in bladder and bowel.

DISCUSSION- A lumbar vertebra fracture can mimic a lumbar disc prolapse because both conditions can cause similar symptoms like low back pain, sciatica, and neurological deficits. These fractures, particularly fractures of the vertebral ring apophysis, can occur in young people and may be difficult to distinguish from a disc herniation on plain X-rays. A CT scan is often essential for a definitive diagnosis, as it can clearly show the fracture, whereas MRI results may be inconclusive in some cases. Both the conditions can have low back pain. A fracture can cause pain that radiates down the leg, similar to the sciatica caused by a herniated disc. In some cases, a vertebral fracture can compress nerves, leading to symptoms like numbness or weakness, just as a disc prolapse can. Lumbar disc herniations are common in the lower lumbar spine (L4-L5 and L5-S1) and can compress the nerves in that area. Certain fractures, like those involving the ring apophysis, can also put pressure on nerves. While MRI is a common tool for diagnosing disc problems, it can sometimes be inconclusive for differentiating between certain fractures and disc herniations. Plain X-rays may also be misleading. A CT scan is often necessary to accurately distinguish between a vertebral fracture and a disc herniation, especially when other imaging is inconclusive. It is important to consider the possibility of a vertebral fracture when a patient presents with symptoms typical of a lumbar disc herniation. In our case there was confusion in making exact diagnosis between vertebral fracture and disc prolapse. There was no tenderness at site of L2 fracture from beginning of disease and history of fall was around one and half months before which hinted towards disc prolapse. Thus, for initial few days conservative management with complete bed rest, analgesics, anti-inflammatory with other supportive therapy were tried but for no relief. Patient was tried for mobilization on two occasions which aggravated the problem, because the compression vertebral fracture got converted into burst fracture, thus leading to impaction of spinal cord by vertebral fragments which caused cord edema which was not there on first MRI report, at the time of beginning of illness. Moreover, absence of tenderness at fracture site can be seen in osteoporotic fractures, as in our case. The one and half month-old history of fall also caused confusion, in fact, at that point of time it must have been minor fracture which gradually progressed over time and sudden precipitation must have been the physiotherapy by homemade massager by house hold help. This must have caused aggravation of fracture, thus soon after patient developed shooting pain which was not relieved by analgesics. The twice effort of mobilizing the patient led to further aggravation of symptoms because of progression of compression fracture to burst fracture, which was evidenced by sudden transient neurological loss after second episode of mobilization. The patient had history of shooting pain radiating to lateral part of thigh which mimicked disc prolapse pain but it was due to compression of spinal cord and nerves emanating at level of L2 and below. The bladder and bowel involvement can be seen both in disc prolapse and traumatic vertebral fractures.

Figure 1- First MRI at beginning of injury showing L2 fracture without cord edema with disc prolapse.

Figure 2- Second MRI before operation showing vertebral fracture pieces causing compression of spinal cord.

Figure 3- Post-operative Chest X-ray showing pulmonary edema.

Figure 4- Post-operative LS spine X-ray showing cement and rods fixed at level, above and below fractured L2 vertebra

Figure 5- Post-operative MRI showing cement fixed in fractured L2 Vertebra.

Figure 6- Post-operative MRI showing collected blood at operative tract site

The first MRI never showed any cord edema which tilted initial diagnosis more in favor of disc prolapse and thus conservative approach and partial mobilization. This also led to partial ignorance of vertebral collapse requiring early stabilization. In the background of old age with osteoporosis and more than sixty percent reduction in L2 vertebral height, early vertebral fixation without conservative approach and partial mobilization, should have been the ideal approach. There is controversial role of steroids but this patient was given injectable steroids for five days, including both pre-operative and post operative period. But then they were transiently stopped which led to slowing of pace of recovery, hence oral steroids were restarted and given over a total period of six weeks in tapering dose. This approach led to increase in pace of functional neurological recovery of the patient. The patient was kept on regular oral bisphosphonates, calcium and vitamin D3 combination to increase bone mass. She was also put on oral multivitamins including zinc and selenium for increasing muscle strength and activity and it really paid off and lead to increase in recovery part. The twice episode of patient going in left heart failure due to withholding of diuretics or rapid infusion of blood and albumin aware about to be very cautious of using blood and blood products in background of heart failure. Moreover, one has to be very cautious about interpreting MRI in post-operative stage, as in our case where collection of small amounts of blood in operative tract which was mimicking pus collection but there was no history of fever, leukocytosis and local tenderness at the site which led to cautious observation and patient never required unwarranted re-exploration of surgical site.

CONCLUSION- The symptoms of vertebral fractures sometimes can lead to confusion with intervertebral disc prolapse and have to be differentiated on a priority basis for preventing damage to the spinal cord, leading to permanent neurological deficit. The use of steroids for reducing cord edema still holds the ground. The management part includes careful observations of comorbid illness and treatment like heart failure in the present case.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST- The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest and no financial support was taken for the above case report.

References

1. Chu EC, Lin A, Huang KHK, Cheung G, Lee WT. A Severe Disc Herniation Mimics Spinal Tumor. *Cureus*. 2023; 15(3): 36545. doi: 10.7759/cureus.36545. PMID: 36968683; PMCID: PMC10033246.
2. Dimogerontas G, Paidakakos NA, Konstantinidis E. Voluminous free disk fragment mimicking an extradural tumor. *Neurol Med Chir (Tokyo)*. 2012; 52(9): 656-8. doi: 10.2176/nmc.52.656. PMID: 23006881.